

IPBES BBA Chapter 6, data management report - Literature review of the civil society actors / IPBES business and biodiversity assessment (Sections 6.3 and 6.4)

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Description

This literature review corresponds to Chapter 6 of the IPBES business and biodiversity assessment. The review was conducted to identify peer reviewed journals and other publications describing the role of Civil Society in the intersection of business and biodiversity. The authors used IPBES' definition of Civil Society from a previous assessment. The authors drafted an outline to identify sections of the chapter to guide the literature review. The review focused on a mix of peer reviewed journals, grey literature, and websites that captured the development and evolution of the civil society sector, and that described the variety of partnerships that occur between civil society actors and business, particularly centered on environment and biodiversity. Finally, a literature review was done on what aspects of the relationship between business and biodiversity can pose barriers to effective collaboration between these sectors. The references that were identified in the literature review were used to support the text in the actions and barriers sections (6.3 and 6.4 respectively) of the chapter.

Process overview

Protocol

- **Type of analysis/search/review:** Search for articles using Google Scholar
- **Search engine:** Google Scholar
- **Timeframe:** From 22 September 2023 to 5 July 2024
- **Search terms:**

1. “Enabling environment” AND “Civil society”

- a. **Sample returned by Google Scholar:** About 1.750.000 results
- b. **Treatment applied:** Examined the top “60” results to identify upto 10 that were relevant based on expert knowledge (A) for suitability for a global assessment. The papers that were focused on a single country experience, or on measuring indexes were not appropriate for report.

2. “Civil society awareness” AND “advocacy Biodiversity”

- c. **Sample returned by Google Scholar:** About 61.600 results
- d. **Treatment applied:** Examined the top “60” results to identify upto 10 that were relevant based on expert knowledge (B) for suitability for a global assessment. Chose the publication that described the role of civil society in raising awareness for forestry and mining businesses on sustainable practices gathered from around the world.

3. “Civil Society” AND “Supply chain certification”

- e. **Sample returned by Google Scholar:** About 208.000 results
- f. **Treatment applied:** Examined the top “60” results to identify upto 10 that were relevant based on expert knowledge (C) for suitability. Chose the publication that described the role of civil society raising awareness for Forestry and mining businesses on sustainable practices gathered from around the world.

4. “Cross Sector Partnerships” AND “Effectiveness”

- a. **Sample returned by Google Scholar:** About 1.390.000 results
- b. **Treatment applied:** Examined the top “60” results to identify upto 10 that were relevant based on expert knowledge (D) for suitability. Chose the publication that described key factors of in the effectiveness of cross sector partnerships and the most important barriers.

Additional files

ID	Name	File Type	Size	Description
A	IPBES_BBA_6.3_07-2024_(A)	.csv	2 KB	References obtained for “Enabling Environment”
B	IPBES_BBA_6.3_07-2024_(B)	.csv	3 KB	References for “Civil society awareness” and “advocacy biodiversity”
C	IPBES_BBA_6.3_07-2024_(C)	.csv	3 KB	References for “Civil society” and “supply chain certification”
D	IPBES_BBA_6.3_07-2024_(D)	.csv	3 KB	References “Cross Sector Partnerships” and “Effectiveness”